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Correlation between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Performance in Mathematics among Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated Correlation between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Performance in Mathematics among Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria. The study was a survey research of the correlational type and sample consisted of twelve mathematics teachers and three hundred (300) SS II Mathematics students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kogi central senatorial zone selected by stratified random sampling techniques from ten (10) senior secondary schools in five (5) local government areas of Kogi Central Senatorial zone. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were raised and formulated respectively to direct the study. Mathematics Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge Assessment Rating Form (MTPKARF) was used to collect data with respect to Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge while students' scores from end of school term examination of the classes taught by the observed mathematics teachers were collected from documentary source in the sampled schools with respect to their academic performance. Data collected were analyzed using regression and multiple regression analysis. The result indicated that: There was significant relationship: between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Academic Performance of students in Mathematics and between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and male and female Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics. Based on the research findings, it was concluded among others that Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge relate directly with and predict students' academic performance. It is recommended among others that the three tier of government in Nigeria should employ qualified mathematics teachers with required education background to teach mathematics in senior secondary schools.

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Keywords: Pedagogical Knowledge, Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge, Student's Academic Performance and Mathematics.

Introduction

Mathematics is one of the school subject that have application to every facet of human endeavor. Shulman (2010) described it as the precursor of scientific discoveries. No Nation, over the world can hope to achieve any measure of scientific or technological advancement without a proper foundation in school mathematics. Gatbonton (2018) opined that mathematics is an indispensable medium by which science expresses, formulates, continues, and communicates itself. It was emphasized that Mathematics has turned into something more than simple calculations; it has become a powerful tool for practical sciences like engineering, industry, and others to mention but a few. It has entered into the development of technology and a great variety of inventions. Thus, the lack of basic mathematics knowledge and skills in any society may isolate such society from the global scientific trend. It is in recognition of the important of mathematics that it is studied as a compulsory subject at both primary and secondary school levels in Nigeria so that every school child will acquire appropriate basic scientific and mathematics knowledge.

However, students' academic performance in Mathematics at the Nigerian secondary school level in WASSCE has improved for the past few years as reported by the WAEC Chief Examiner's Report (2021, 2022, and 2023) based on the statistics of students with A's, B's, and C's. With this development in terms of performance, more is needed to be done to maintain the standard. However, this does not mean that success has been attained in teaching mathematics as there are lots of factors that still militate against teachers' effort to achieve the primary objectives of teaching and learning of mathematics at the secondary school level that must be addressed. Prominent among these factors are teachers' Motivation level, students' interest in mathematics and teachers' Competency (i.e. Teachers' pedagogical knowledge, Content knowledge and acquisition of Skills). The focus of this study is on teachers' pedagogical knowledge as a component of teachers' competency.

According to Rodgers and Raider-Roth, (2010), many a teacher is knowledgeable of his or her subject matter without necessarily being able to decompress it in a way that he or she will make it accessible to his or her students. However, having pedagogical knowledge is the way to decompress the subject matter knowledge. In this respect, teachers' pedagogical knowledge is the ability of a teacher to adopt diverse suitable

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strategies and teaching methods while impacting knowledge of the subject matter in a manner that makes sense to the students. Shulman (2010) define it as any theory or belief about teaching and the process of learning to plan and the process of learning that a teacher possesses that influences that teacher's teaching. This process includes the implementation, problem solving and teaching strategies, questioning techniques and assessment (Hudson, 2017). Tak-wah and Yiu-Chi (2019) also described it as knowing the ways of representing and formulating the subject-matter and making it comprehensive to students.

Furthermore, Elit and Sibel (2017), indicated that pedagogical knowledge includes the ways of representing content that make it comprehensible to learners and an understanding of what makes the learning of specific topics easy or difficult. Monica and Helen (2017) on the other hand emphasize that pedagogical knowledge includes: knowledge of multiple ways of representing content to students which relies on the teacher's understanding of the content and has its purpose in the transformation of the content into a form that students will understand such as illustration, examples, explanations and demonstrations; an understanding of what makes topics easy or difficult; knowledge of students' typical preconceptions and misconceptions; strategies for helping students reorganize their understanding; knowledge of student thinking and knowing the relationships among topics procedures and concepts. The study therefore see pedagogical knowledge of mathematics teachers as the knowledge of how to teach mathematics.

To cope with the problem of maintaining/keeping and improving upon the standard already attained in academic performance in mathematics in senior secondary school in Nigeria, there is need to produce and have competent teachers who can effectively teach and motivate students to learn mathematics. Thus, education courses offered in Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), University undergraduate programme, Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE), Masters and Ph. D, are meant to help develop teacher's knowledge about teaching. Also, several years of teaching experience will also help build upon that knowledge to make it more specialized and useful. Mathematics teachers must therefore, possess pedagogical knowledge of their content area in order to facilitate students' learning. This study carried out investigation to determine if teachers' pedagogical knowledge is a predictor to students' academic performance in mathematics.

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Moreover, a growing body of research has shown that students' academic performance is influenced by teachers' pedagogy knowledge and yet, others are in contradiction. The study conducted by Baumert et al (2010), Bayer and Davis (2011) and Olorunsola (2019) pointed out that there was significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' academic performance in mathematics including students' academic performance on gender bases. But contrary results were obtained by Ladipo, (2013); Olabisi, Alabi and Henry (2017) whose study indicated that there is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' academic performance in mathematics and that the former is not a predictor of the later. Thus this study examined whether teachers' pedagogical knowledge significantly relate with and predict senior secondary school students' academic performance in mathematics in Central Senatorial Zone, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

It has been noted that students' academic performance in Mathematics at the Nigerian secondary school level in WASSCE has improved for the past few years as reported by the WAEC Chief Examiner's Report (2021, 2022, and 2023) based on the statistics of students with A's, B's, and C's. With this development in terms of performance, more is needed to be done to maintain the standard. However, this does not mean that success has been attained in teaching mathematics as there are lots of factors that still militate against teachers' effort to achieve the primary objectives of teaching and learning of mathematics at the secondary school level that must be addressed. Prominent among these factors are teachers' Motivation level, students' interest in mathematics and teachers' Competency (Teachers' pedagogical knowledge, Content knowledge and acquisition of Skills). It was on this note that the study investigated, 'Correlation between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and performance in mathematics among secondary school students in Kogi State, Nigeria.'

Objectives of the Study

The study investigated Correlation between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Performance in Mathematics among Senior Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study determine if:

1. Teachers' pedagogical knowledge predict students' academic performance in mathematics.
2. Teachers' pedagogical knowledge predict male and female students' academic performance in mathematics.

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Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between Teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' Academic performance in mathematics?
2. What is the relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and male & female students' academic performance in mathematics?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' academic performance in mathematics.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and male & female students' academic performance in mathematics.

Methodology

The study used survey research design of the correlational type which according to Launer (2006), establish relationship between two or more variables that has manifested already hence, no manipulation of existing phenomenon is required. The variables in this research work has manifested already hence, no manipulation of existing phenomenon is required and emphasis is on association between the variables. The researcher used assessment rating for teachers' pedagogical knowledge and the students' performance scores were collected from the examination administered to the students by the observed mathematics teachers in the sample schools. The researcher observed the sampled mathematics teachers in the sample classes in each sample schools each on three occasions while teaching throughout a whole school term and take the average of their pedagogical knowledge rating. Also, the end of term mathematics examination scores of the students they taught were collected which form the data for the study.

The target population for this study embraced all the Senior Secondary two (SSII) Mathematics teachers and SS II students in Kogi Central Senatorial Zone for 2023/2024 academic session. This consisted of 55 teachers teaching Mathematics at SS II classes and 2,139 SS II Students (1080 males & 1059 females) respectively from forty four senior secondary schools in Kogi Central Senatorial Zone. Sample consisted of fifteen mathematics teachers and three hundred (300) SS II students selected by stratified random sampling techniques from ten (10) senior secondary schools in five (5) local government areas of Kogi Central Senatorial zone.

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Data collected for the study was through the use of 20 items Mathematics Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge Assessment Rating Form (MTPKARF) and students' examination scores conducted by the observed mathematics teachers at the end of the school term. The Mathematics Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge Assessment Rating Form was adapted from (Eric Zhi Feng LIU^a and Chun Hung LIN, 2010) used in this study to collect information about teachers' pedagogical knowledge in teaching mathematics. The rating ranged from 0 to 5, where 0 stand for lowest score while 5 for the highest score. For each item the teachers were scored from 0 to 5 and the maximum obtainable score for the 20 items is 100%. The scoring was done by the researcher through observation while the teachers were teaching. Students' scores from end of school term examination of the classes taught by the observed mathematics teachers were collected from documentary source in the sampled schools with respect to their academic performance.

The MTPKARF was field tested on a sample of 5 SSII mathematics teachers in a school that was not part of the study. The instrument have reliability coefficient of 0.83 using test retest method and Pearson Product Moment Correlation for data analysis. Examination questions set by mathematics teachers were internally moderated by the head of department and some senior colleagues. Marked examination scripts were vetted by an internal examiner to ensure internal quality controls. Data collected were analyzed using regression and multiple regression analysis to address the research questions and test the null hypothesis

Presentation of Results

The data collected from the study were analysed to address the research questions and test the null hypotheses using regression and multiple regression analysis as follow:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' academic performance in mathematics.

To test the null hypothesis and address the corresponding research question, regression analysis was used as shown in Table 1a and 1b.

Table 1a: Regression Analysis of Prediction between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Students academic Performance in Mathematics

Model	R	Change Statistics
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	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	R Square Change	F Change	Df1	Df2	Sig. Change	F	Durbin-Watson
1	.716	.465	.458	19.132	.385	37.845	1	56	.000	1.973

Predictors: (Constant). Pedagogical Knowledge

Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Performance

The results of the Regression analysis as shown in Table 1a, revealed F ratio of 1.973 and df of 1, 56 and computed p value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 alpha level, indicating that teachers' pedagogical knowledge significantly related with and predicted the students' academic performance in mathematics. This implies that the null hypothesis H_{01} was rejected and alternative hypothesis retained. The predictor factors for the relationship are: $a = 20.234$ and $b = .716$ as presented in Table 1b. The regression equation is $y = 20.234 + .716x$. Table 1b contains the summary of the test of the contribution of each predictor in the regression analysis.

Table 1b: Coefficients^a of Correlation between Teachers' Pedagogical, Knowledge and Students' Performance in Mathematics

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	20.234	5.011		4.318	.000
Pedagogical Knowledge	.644	.102	.716	6.241	.000

As shown on Table 1b, the unstandardized regression coefficient of pedagogical knowledge was 0.644 and Standardized regression coefficients was 0.716 which were higher than the Regression critical value of 0.4. Hence, the relationship between the two variables is a high direct relation.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and male & female students' academic performance in mathematics

To test the null hypothesis and address the corresponding research question, multiple regression analysis was used as presented in Table 2a and 2b.

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Table 2a: Multiple Regression Analysis of Prediction between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Male and Female Students Academic Performance in Mathematics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of estimate	tChange Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Change	Square Change	Df1	Df2	Sig. Chang	
1	.834	.798	.791	6.989	.898	105.971	3	54	.001	1.498

Predictors: (Constant), Pedagogical Knowledge

Dependent Variable: Male and Female Students Academic Performance

The results of the Regression analysis as shown in Table 2a, revealed F ratio of 1.498 and df of 3, 54 and computed p value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 alpha level, indicating that teachers' pedagogical knowledge significantly related with and predicted the male and female students' academic performance in mathematics. This implies that the null hypothesis H_{02} was rejected and alternative hypothesis retained. The predictor factors for the relationship are: $a = 11.329$ and $b_1 = .634$ and $b_2 = .595$ as presented in Table 2b. Table 2b contains the summary of the test of the contribution of each predictor in the regression analysis.

Table 2b: Coefficients^a of Correlation between Teachers Pedagogical Knowledge and Male and Female Students' Performance in Mathematics.

Model	Unstandardised Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
Constant	11.329	4.318		-1.324	.005
Male Students' Academic Performance	.513	.121	.634	.296	.006
Female Students' Academic Performance	.499	.153	.595	3.134	.002

As shown on Table 2b, the unstandardized regression coefficient of male and female students' academic performance were 0.513 and 0.499 respectively, their Standardized regression coefficients were 0.634 and 0.595 respectively which were higher than the Regression critical value of 0.4. Hence, the relationship between the teachers'

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pedagogical knowledge and male and female students' academic performance in mathematics is a high direct relation.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the study as presented in Table 1a and 1b and likewise in Table 2a and 2b showed that mathematics teachers' pedagogical knowledge had a direct relationship on and is a good predictor of students' academic performance in mathematics. This implies that the level of teachers' pedagogical knowledge in teaching mathematics determine how well the students performed academically irrespective of the students' gender. It can however be deduced that for a mathematics teacher to be successful in the classroom, be able to impart mathematics knowledge to the students adequately and to achieve the require result better (student's performance) he/she must be well grounded in the methodology of teaching the subject. This could only be ensured if the person delivering mathematics instruction is a trainee teacher. These result agreed with the outcome of what is obtained in the study of Baumert etal (2010) and Olorunsola (2019) but contradicts the finding of Ladipo (2013) and Olabisi, Alabi and Henry (2017) who reported that teachers' pedagogical knowledge did not significantly relate with and predict students' academic performance in mathematics including male and female students' performance on gender bases.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that Mathematics Teachers' pedagogical knowledge has direct relationship with and is a predictor to students' academic performance in mathematics irrespective of their gender. This implies that the more sound Mathematics Teachers' pedagogical knowledge is the better their students' academic performance in mathematics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research work, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Government should endeavor to employ only qualified trained mathematics teachers to teach mathematics in senior secondary schools in Kogi Central Senatorial zone.
2. Unqualified mathematics teachers in senior secondary schools should be provided opportunity of in-service training for them to be train as a professional teacher in programmes such as institute of Education's Professional Diploma in Education (PDE) Ahmadu Bello University Zaria or Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) offered in the Nigeria Universities.

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3. The Federal and State government should engage in training and retraining of senior secondary school mathematics teachers in service in their domain through seminar, workkshop or conference to update their pedagogical knowledge in order to move along with the current trend of information and communication technology as it relates to teaching and learning.

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